

Supporting Information: Polarity-induced selective area epitaxy of GaN nanowires

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Effect of Si deposition on surface morphology

We have analyzed the influence of Si deposition on surface morphology by atomic force microscopy (AFM). In Fig. S1 we present a micrograph of an as-grown GaN layer, i. e., without Si deposition. The surface is characterized by atomic steps and flat hillocks. The latter originate from spiral step-flow growth around screw dislocations. The root mean square roughness is 1.2 nm. Figure S2 presents atomic force micrographs acquired at different positions of a sample after depositing Si for 30 min at 790°C on the GaN buffer layer (as described in the manuscript). The micrographs reveal the formation of three-dimensional (3D) islands. The region in between the islands becomes rougher and exhibit a meander-like structure. This morphology is very different from that observed for the bare GaN surface, which corresponds to a GaN layer grown at 790°C without Si deposition, demonstrating that both the formation of 3D islands as well as the overall roughing of the surface is a direct consequence of Si deposition.

The density of 3D islands on the surface after Si deposition is found to monotonically increase from the edge of the sample [Fig. S2(a)] towards its center [Fig. S2(c)] due to the gradient in the Si deposition rate caused by the lack of substrate rotation. The statistical analysis of the atomic force

Figure S1: $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ atomic force micrograph showing the surface morphology of the starting GaN surface.

micrographs indicates that the 3D islands have an average diameter and height of about 25 and 30 nm, respectively. The island density in the investigated regions is found to increase from about 4 to $6 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ when moving from the edge towards the center of the sample, corresponding to an increase of $\approx 50\%$. This density is lower than the measured GaN nanowire (NW) density for the sample grown after a Si pre-deposition time of 23.5 minutes, suggesting that the formation of the NWs is not only triggered by the presence of 3D islands.

Figure S2: (a)-(c) $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ atomic force micrographs collected at different positions of a GaN sample where Si was deposited for 30 min and without further GaN growth. The GaN surface is rough and several 3D islands are observed on the surface, whose density increases from the edge (a) towards the center (c) of the sample.

Figure S3: Evolution of the RHEED pattern along the $[1\bar{1}20]$ azimuth during the growth of the sample for which Si was deposited for 10 min. The streaky pattern of the GaN buffer layer before exposing it to Si (a) indicates that it is smooth. The spotty pattern of the GaN buffer layer shortly after opening the Si shutter (b) at a substrate temperature of 790°C reveals the roughening of the growth front. No further significant changes were observed upon GaN overgrowth (c).

Figure S4: High-resolution cross-sectional transmission electron micrographs showing the interface between the GaN buffer layer and three different GaN NWs. The buffer layer is faceted as a result of Si deposition. The contrast variation across the interface reveals the formation of a 1–2ML thick $(\text{Ga,Si})(\text{Si,N})$ interlayer which reverses the polarity from Ga to N.

Evolution of the reflection high-energy electron diffraction pattern during growth

The roughening of the GaN layer during Si deposition was also observed in-situ by reflection high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED). Figure S3 presents the evolution of the RHEED pattern along the $[11\bar{2}0]$ azimuth during the preparation of a sample where Si was deposited for 10 min. The RHEED pattern from the starting GaN buffer layer is shown in Fig. S3(a). The streaky pattern indicates a smooth starting surface, in good agreement with the atomic force micrograph shown in Fig. S1. About one minute after opening the Si shutter, the RHEED pattern becomes spotty [Fig. S3(b)] revealing a significant roughening of the growth front. This transition is found to occur for a nominal Si deposited thickness of about 0.05 MLs, suggesting that Si alone can be hardly responsible for the formation of the 3D structures required to observe a spotty RHEED pattern. In agreement with this observation, the position of the spots in the pattern shown in Fig. S3(b) indicates the presence of a hexagonal lattice with the same c and a lattice parameters as those of wurtzite GaN (within the experimental resolution of our experiments). Interestingly, we do not observe any pattern that could be ascribed to cubic Si. This result indicates that the deposition of Si at 790°C induces a strong reorganization of the surface whereas Si atoms diffuse most likely into GaN. The 3D islands observed in Fig. S2 are thus not necessarily composed of Si but may primarily be consist of GaN. This scenario is compatible with the transmission electron micrographs shown in Figs. 5(c) and 5(d), which demonstrate the presence of a (Ga,Si)(Si,N) alloy after GaN overgrowth. Finally, as shown in Fig. S3(c), the RHEED pattern does not exhibit any significant changes after Si nitridation and further GaN growth.

For the other samples investigated in this work, which are characterized by different Si deposition times, we observed an analogous evolution of the RHEED pattern along the different growth stages.

Additional cross-sectional transmission electron micrographs

Figure S4 presents additional highly-magnified bright-field transmission electron micrographs taken at the interfaces between the GaN buffer layer and three different GaN NWs. All the micrographs correspond to the sample where Si was pre-deposited for 60 min. As in the case of Fig. 5, the present micrographs reveal the formation of a rough interface bound by semi-polar planes. In all the micrographs shown in Fig. S4, we observe the formation of a 1–2 ML thick crystalline interlayer. As discussed in the manuscript, this interlayer is coherent, free of dislocations, and reverses the polarity from Ga to N. The high contrast variation across the interlayer implies a substantial concentration of substitutionally incorporated Si atoms. Therefore a (Ga,Si)(Si,N) alloy forms on certain regions of the semi-polar planes that constitute the interface between the buffer layer and the GaN NWs.

Representative scanning electron micrographs used to assess the density and diameter of GaN NWs

Low magnification plan-view scanning electron micrographs collected from one edge to the other of the wafer are shown in Figure S5 for the samples with a Si pre-deposition time of 21.5 [Figs. S5(a)–S5(d)] and 23.5 min [Figs. S5(e)–S5(h)], respectively. Representative highly magnified plan-view scanning electron micrographs of the same samples shown in Fig. S5 are presented in Fig. S6. From the analysis of several highly magnified micrographs, the density and average diameter of the GaN NWs are assessed as a function of the position across the wafer. For the latter, the NW top facets are approximated by circles.

In the region of the samples with low NW density, an accurate determination of the NW diameter from the analysis of plan-view micrographs is hampered by the lack of sufficient contrast between the NW top facets and the surrounding faceted layer [as indicated by the orange circles in Figs. S6(a), S6(b), S6(c), S6(e), and S6(f)]. For this reason, in these regions the average NW

Figure S5: Plan-view scanning electron micrographs collected from one edge to the other of the wafer for the samples where GaN NWs were formed after depositing Si for 21.5 (a)–(d) and 23.5 min (e)–(h), respectively.

Figure S6: Representative highly magnified plan-view scanning electron micrographs collected from one edge to the other of the wafer for the NW samples grown after depositing Si for 21.5 (a)–(d) and 23.5 min (e)–(h), respectively. The orange circles in (a), (b), (c), (e) and (f) highlight some of those NWs which diameter cannot be assessed from the analysis of the present plan-view micrographs due to the insufficient contrast between their top facets and the surrounding faceted layer.

Figure S7: Representative cross-sectional scanning electron micrographs of the GaN NWs formed on the samples where Si was pre-deposited for 21.5 (a) and 23.5 min (b). Both images were collected in the regions of the samples exhibiting the lowest NW density.

diameter is not calculated from the analysis of plan-view but cross-sectional scanning electron micrographs. Representative cross-sectional micrographs collected in the region of the wafers showing the lowest NW density are shown in Figs. S7(a) and S7(b) for the samples grown after a Si pre-deposition time of 21.5 and 23.5 min, respectively. Due to the very low NW density, the average NW diameter is calculated from several micrographs in order to have a sufficiently large statistics.